

DESIGN OF STATISTICALLY OPTIMAL MORPHOLOGICAL OPERATORS

Junior Barrera¹ and Edward R. Dougherty²

¹ Dept. of Computer Science, University of São Paulo,
Rua do Matão, 1010, 05508-900 São Paulo, BRAZIL

e-mail: jb@ime.usp.br

² Dept. of Electrical Engineering, Texas A & M University
College Station, 77840 - TX, United States

e-mail: edward@ee.tamu.edu

ABSTRACT

This paper recalls a general framework for the design of optimal nonlinear digital filters: the statistically optimal morphological operators. Optimal filters are designed using the algebraic decomposition structure of Mathematical Morphology and observations of input-output pairs of signals or images.

1 Introduction

A central problem in Digital Signal Processing (DSP) or Digital Image Analysis (DIA) is the design of signal or image processing procedures to perform desired tasks. Usually, the goal is to find a procedure that has effects similar to the ones described by a collection of examples.

A family of digital signals or images can be modeled by a discrete random function [1]. A procedure used in DSP or DIA can be modeled by a function mapping, also called *operator*, applied on a discrete random function.

Procedure design from examples can be modeled by statistical estimation (or learning) of function operators from observation of input-output signal or image pairs. Given an input $\mathbf{S}$ and an ideal output $\mathbf{I}$ random functions, known just by some of their realizations, we should find a function operator Ψ such that $\Psi(\mathbf{S})$ is statistically close to $\mathbf{I}$. This problem can be formulated as an optimization problem: given a family $\mathcal{I}$ of function operators, where the distance between the ideal output $\mathbf{I}$ and estimated random function $\Psi(\mathbf{S})$ is measured by a statistical error measure, the operator $\Psi_{opt} \in \mathcal{I}$ is called optimal in $\mathcal{I}$ if it posses minimum error. Additionally, if all operators in $\mathcal{I}$ can be characterized by some algebraic representation that depends on a set of parameters, then optimization can be viewed as finding the best representation parameters.

Mathematical Morphology (MM) is a general algebraic framework to represent lattice operators [2] [3]. MM can be understood as a formal language, where lattice operators are represented in terms of four simple families of lattice operators: dilations, anti-dilation, erosions and anti-erosions. These *elementary operators* are concatenated via the operations of composition, union and intersection and are characterized by lattice elements

called *structuring elements*. The set of functions that represent signals or images, with the usual partial order relation, is a lattice and, therefore, signal and image operators can be represented by MM. Thus, an optimal image or signal operator may be designed by the estimation of the structuring elements that characterize the elementary operators that represent this operator.

A key family of function operators are the *W-operators*. These operators are translation invariant and locally defined in the time domain of the signal or the space domain of the image. Any W-operator can be characterized by a function, called *computational function*, whose domain is a restriction of signals to a time window or images to a space window. These computational functions can be represented by a single phrase structure, called the *standard morphological representation*. Thus, design of W-operators can be seen as estimation of the structuring elements of the standard representation. Two particular families of W-operators are the aperture [4] and stack filters [5]. The aperture filters have computational functions that depend on a small subset of the signal or image range, while the stack filters are increasing operators that have computational functions which depend on Boolean functions.

Following this introduction, Section 2 recalls the standard morphological representation for finite lattice operators. Section 3 recalls the representation of lattice to chain operators. Section 4 gives the characterization of W-operators. Section 5 presents the design of W-operators as a learning problem. Finally, Section 6 presents some reflections about the general non linear filter design framework recalled here.

2 Representation of lattice operators

Let $\mathcal{L}_1$ and $\mathcal{L}_2$ be two complete lattices. We denote by $Fun[\mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2]$ the set of all functions from $\mathcal{L}_1$ to $\mathcal{L}_2$. The elements of $Fun[\mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2]$ will be called *mappings* or *operators*.

Let $\psi \in Fun[\mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2]$ and let $\mathcal{X}$ be a subset of $\mathcal{L}_1$. We will denote by $\psi(\mathcal{X})$ the image of $\mathcal{X}$ through ψ .

An operator $\epsilon \in Fun[\mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2]$ is called an *erosion* if and only if (iff)

$$\epsilon(\bigwedge \mathcal{X}) = \bigwedge \epsilon(\mathcal{X}),$$

for every $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_1$.

Let $A \in \mathcal{L}_1$. An example of an erosion is the operator ϵ_A from $\mathcal{L}_1$ to $\{0, 1\}$ given by:

$$\epsilon_A(X) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } A \leq X \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{L}_1$.

An operator $\delta^a \in Fun[\mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2]$ is called an *anti-dilation* iff

$$\psi(\bigvee \mathcal{X}) = \bigwedge \psi(\mathcal{X}),$$

for every $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_1$.

Let $B \in \mathcal{L}_1$. An example of an anti-dilation is the operator δ_B^a from $\mathcal{L}_1$ to $\{0, 1\}$ given by:

$$\delta_B^a(X) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } X \leq B \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{L}_1$.

Let $A, B \in \mathcal{L}_1$ such that $A \leq B$. The operator $\lambda_{A,B}$ from $\mathcal{L}_1$ to $\{0, 1\}$, given by

$$\lambda_{A,B} = \epsilon_A \wedge \delta_B^a,$$

is called a *binary sup-generating operator*.

A subset $\mathcal{X}$ of a poset $\mathcal{L}$ is an interval in $\mathcal{L}$ iff there exists two elements A and B of $\mathcal{L}$ such that

$$A \leq X \leq B \Leftrightarrow X \in \mathcal{X},$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{L}$.

Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{L}_1)$ be the power set of $\mathcal{L}_1$ and $Fun[\mathcal{L}_2, \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{L}_1)]$ be the set of functions from $\mathcal{L}_2$ to $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{L}_1)$. The *kernel* $\mathcal{K}(\psi)$ of ψ is the function in $Fun[\mathcal{L}_2, \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{L}_1)]$ given by:

$$\mathcal{K}(\psi)(Y) = \{X \in \mathcal{L}_1 : Y \leq \psi(X)\},$$

for every $\psi \in Fun[\mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2]$ and $Y \in \mathcal{L}_2$ [6] [7].

Theorem 2.1 Any operator ψ from $\mathcal{L}_1$ to $\mathcal{L}_2$ has the following constructive sup-decomposition:

$$\bigvee \{Y \in \mathcal{L}_2 : \bigvee \{\lambda_{A,B}(X) : [A, B] \subseteq \mathcal{K}(\psi)(Y)\} = 1\},$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{L}_1$.

The constructive decomposition of operators between complete lattices given by Theorem 2.1 can be simplified in the sense that a smaller set of sup-generating operators may be enough to perform the decomposition.

Let $Max(\mathcal{L})$ denote the set of maximal elements of the poset $\mathcal{L}$. The *basis* $\mathbf{B}(\psi)$ of the operator ψ is the function given by, for any $Y \in \mathcal{L}_2$,

$$\mathbf{B}(\psi)(Y) = Max(\{[A, B] : [A, B] \subseteq \mathcal{K}(\psi)(Y)\}).$$

Theorem 2.2 Let $\mathcal{L}_1$ to $\mathcal{L}_2$ be two finite lattices. If ψ is an operator from $\mathcal{L}_1$ to $\mathcal{L}_2$, then

$$\bigvee \{Y \in \mathcal{L}_2 : \bigvee \{\lambda_{A,B}(X) : [A, B] \in \mathbf{B}(\psi)(Y)\} = 1\},$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{L}_1$, and ψ is said to have a minimal decomposition by a set of binary sup-generating operators.

3 Representation of lattice to chain operators

From now on let us suppose that $\mathcal{L}_2$ is the bounded chain of positive integers $M = [0, m]$. Then $\mathcal{K} = \{\mathcal{K}(\psi)(y) : y \in M\}$ also constitutes a bounded chain in $(\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{L}_1), \subseteq)$, for every operator $\psi \in Fun[\mathcal{L}_1, M]$.

Theorem 3.1 Every operator $\psi \in Fun[\mathcal{L}_1, M]$ has the following sup-decomposition:

$$\psi(X) = \bigvee_{y=1}^m \bigvee \{\lambda_{A,B}(X) : [A, B] \in \mathbf{B}(\psi)(y)\},$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{L}_1$.

This result follows from Theorem 2.2, with $\mathcal{L}_2 = M$, the fact that M and $\mathcal{K}$ are bounded chains, and the existence of integer addition in M .

Let $Fun[W, M]$ denote the set of functions from a finite set W to M . Elements of $Fun[W, M]$ will be denoted by the small case letter u . For every $u \in Fun[W, M]$ and $y \in M$, the threshold of u at y is the subset $T_y(u)$ of W given by

$$T_y(u) = \{x \in W : y \leq u(x)\}.$$

An operator ψ from $Fun[W, M]$ to M is called a *sup-Boolean reductible operator* if there exists a function β_ψ from $\mathcal{P}(W)$ to $\{0, 1\}$ such that

$$\psi(u) = \bigvee \{y \in M : \beta_\psi(T_y(u)) = 1\},$$

for every $u \in Fun[W, M]$. Applying the sup-decomposition for β_ψ , we have

$$\psi(u) = \bigvee \{y \in M : \bigvee \{\lambda_{A,B}(T_y(u)) : [A, B] \in \mathbf{B}(\beta_\psi)\} = 1\},$$

for every $u \in Fun[W, M]$, where $\mathbf{B}(\beta_\psi)$ denotes $\mathbf{B}(\beta_\psi)(1)$. Particularly, when β_ψ is increasing the last decomposition simplifies to:

$$\psi(u) = \bigvee_{y=1}^m \bigvee \{\lambda_{A,B}(T_y(u)) : [A, B] \in \mathbf{B}(\beta_\psi)\},$$

for every $u \in Fun[W, M]$, because $T_z(u) \subseteq T_y(u)$ and $\beta_\psi(T_z(u)) \leq \beta_\psi(T_y(u))$ for every $y \leq z$. Such operators are called *stack filters* in the literature.

4 Representation of W-operators

Let E be a non empty set that is an Abelian group with respect to a binary operation denoted by $+$, and let l and m be two positive integers, which define the set of gray-levels $L = [0, l]$ and $M = [0, m]$. An *image* is a mapping from E to L or from E to M . Images will be denoted by f . The set of all images from E to L (respec., M) will be denoted $Fun[E, L]$ (respec., $Fun[E, M]$).

For every $f \in Fun[E, L]$ and $z \in E$, the translation of f by z is the function f_z given by

$$f_z(x) = f(x - z).$$

for every $x \in E$.

An *image operator* is a mapping from $Fun[E, L]$ to $Fun[E, M]$. Image operators will be denoted by capital Greek letters $\Lambda, \Psi, \dots$

Let W be a finite subset of E and f/W be the restriction of the image f to W . A *computational function* is a mapping from $Fun[W, L]$ to M . A *W-operator* Ψ is an image operator that is characterized by a computational function ψ by

$$\Psi(f)(x) = \psi(f_{-x}/W),$$

for every $x \in E$ and $f \in Fun[E, L]$.

Let $\Lambda_{A,B}$ denote the W-operator from $Fun[E, L]$ to $Fun[E, \{0,1\}]$ that is characterized by the sup-generating operator $\lambda_{A,B}$, that is,

$$\Lambda_{A,B}(f)(x) = \lambda_{A,B}(f_{-x}/W),$$

for every $f \in Fun[E, L]$ and $x \in E$.

Theorem 4.1 *Every W-operator Ψ from $Fun[E, L]$ to $Fun[E, M]$, characterized by the computational function ψ from $Fun[W, L]$ to M , has the following sup-decomposition:*

$$\Psi(f) = \sum_{y=1}^m \bigvee \{ \Lambda_{A,B}(f) : [A, B] \in \mathbf{B}(\psi)(y) \},$$

for every $f \in Fun[E, L]$.

5 Learning W-operators

In the last section, we have seen that each W-operator is characterized by a computational function. Therefore, the design of W-operators can be performed in the space of computational functions. Furthermore, if the computational function can be characterized by a Boolean function the search space reduces to this family of functions. In the following, we present the PAC learning[8] theory for binary concepts and show how it can be applied for the design of Boolean functions that characterize W-operators.

The Probably Approximately Correct – PAC – framework was introduced in the seminal paper by L. G. Valiant[9]. Since then, many contributions to the so-called computational learning theory has formalized the idea of reaching an accurate model of some process by drawing a random sample of examples - a machine learning some concept from examples.

Let $\mathcal{A}$ be a set of *instances*. For example, if W is a rectangle, $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{P}(W)$ are all the bidimensional arrays defined on W . A *concept* over $\mathcal{A}$ is a subset $\mathcal{C} \subset \mathcal{A}$. For example, $\mathcal{C}$ may be the set of all pixel arrays representing the letter “A”, i.e., the set of all *positive* examples of “A”. Equivalently, we may define a concept $\mathcal{C}$ as a Boolean mapping $\psi_{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ such that $\psi_{\mathcal{C}}(X) = 1$ iff $X \in \mathcal{C}$. Thus, a concept ψ may be any Boolean function that characterizes a W-operator. A

concept class $\{\mathcal{C}_i\}$ is a collection of concepts over $\mathcal{A}$. For example, $\{\mathcal{C}_i\}$ may be the class of all letters. A pair $(X, b) \in \mathcal{A} \times \{0,1\}$ that expresses if X satisfies the concept $\mathcal{C}$ or not, is called an example for $\mathcal{C}$. If $b = 1$, the example is *positive*, otherwise it is *negative*. A *learning algorithm* has access to positive and negative examples of an unknown *target concept* ψ , chosen from a known concept class $\{\mathcal{C}_i\}$. A learning algorithm gives an estimate of any target concept $\mathcal{C} \in \{\mathcal{C}_i\}$.

Let *Oracle*($\psi, \mathcal{D}$) be a procedure that, whenever asked, provides a labeled example $\langle X, \psi(X) \rangle$, where X is drawn randomly and independently from the distribution $\mathcal{D}$. When designing morphological operators, the oracle is generated from observed ideal pairs of images. A learning algorithm has access to this *Oracle*($\psi, \mathcal{D}$) when learning the target concept $\psi \in \{\mathcal{C}_i\}$. We would like a learning algorithm to have the following properties:

1. *Oracle*($\psi, \mathcal{D}$) is asked a relatively small number of times;
2. the computation time to learn is small;
3. the algorithm outputs ϕ (called *hypothesis concept*) with a small error.

Let l be a function from $\{0,1\}^2$ to $[0, \infty]$. l is called *loss function*, because it gives the cost of a miss classification.

Definition 5.1 (*Generalized PAC Learning*) *An algorithm L that generates hypothesis ϕ , is a Generalized Probably Approximately Correct (GPAC) learning algorithm for $\{\mathcal{C}_i\}$ if, for all $0 < \epsilon, \delta < 1/2$ there exists a positive integer $m(\epsilon, \delta)$ such that $m \geq m(\epsilon, \delta)$ implies*

$$P[l(r(\phi), r(\phi_{opt})) < \epsilon] > 1 - \delta,$$

for every joint distribution $(\mathcal{D}, b)$.

The simplest loss function is the *Mean Absolute Error* (MAE) loss function, defined by: $l(u, v) = |u - v|$, for $u, v \in \{0,1\}$. The optimal MAE concept ϕ_{MAE} is given by

$$\phi_{MAE}(X) = 1 \Leftrightarrow P(1|X) > 0.5.$$

6 Conclusion

There are a set of remarkable properties that make the MM framework quite adequate for the design of digital signals or image operators [10] [11]. First, it represents true digital operators, without approximations (as is the case of the linear theories). Second, it is enough to represent any discrete operator. Third, the estimation algorithms are always convergent, because of their discrete nature. Forth, the lattice structure that is behind the standard representation is very adequate for

the modeling of prior knowledge about the operators to be designed.

Modeling of prior knowledge is fundamental for solving complex real world problems such as the ones that depend on large windows. Some examples of techniques for modeling of prior knowledge on this structure are the switching algorithm [12] [13] for increasing operators, the envelope design [14] and the pyramid design [15] [16].

The development of techniques for designing operators in the MM framework depends on the development of a discrete optimization theory that is an intersection of concepts from Lattice Algebra, Probability, Statistics and Combinatory. Lattice Algebra gives representation structures for signal, images and operators. Probabilistic models may be defined on image and signal representation models. Statistical measures constitute the metrics for formulating the optimization problem. The algebraic structures, the probabilistic model and the statistical measures define combinatorial optimization problems that require efficient algorithms. Besides, the search of efficient equivalent morphological representations for operators usually is a hard combinatorial problem.

We presented a powerful nonlinear digital filters design approach, supported by a strong Mathematical basis, that has the potential to become a general theory for filter design. The mathematical challenges in this way are absolutely non trivial and in many problems the computational power required is very large, but the mathematical structure is properly set and the computer technology is moving very fast. Hence, we believe in a promising future.

References

- [1] J. Goutsias. Morphological Analysis of Discrete Randon Sets. *Journal of Mathematical Imaging and Vision*, 2:193–215, 1992.
- [2] Jean Serra. *Image Analysis and Mathematical Morphology, Volume 2: Theoretical Advances*. Academic Press, London, 1988.
- [3] H. J. A. M. Heijmans. *Morphological Image Operators*. Academic Press, 1994.
- [4] J. Barrera and E. R. Dougherty. Representation of gray-scale windowed operators. In H. Heijmans, editor, *Mathematical Morphology and its Applications to Image and Signal Processing*, pages 19–26. Kluwer Academic Publishers, June 1998.
- [5] N. S. T. Hirata, J. Barrera, and E. R. Dougherty. Design of Statistically Optimal Stack Filters. In J. Stolfi and C. L. Tozzi, editors, *Proc. of Sibgrapi'99*, pages 265–274, Campinas, SP, Brazil, 1999.
- [6] G. J. F. Banon and J. Barrera. Decomposition of mappings between complete lattices by mathematical morphology, Part I: general lattices. *Signal Processing*, 30:299–327, 1993.
- [7] J. Barrera, R. Terada, R. Hirata Jr, and N. S. T. Hirata. Automatic Programming of Morphological Machines by PAC Learning. *Fundamenta Informaticae*, 41(1-2):229–258, January 2000.
- [8] M. Anthony and N. Biggs. *Computational Learning Theory - An Introduction*. Cambridge University Press, 1992.
- [9] L. G. Valiant. A theory of the learnable. *Communications of the ACM*, 27(11):1134–1142, 1984.
- [10] E. R. Dougherty and J. Barrera. *Non linear filters for image processing*, chapter Computational Gray-Scale Operators. SPIE and IEEE Press, 1998.
- [11] E. R. Dougherty and J. Barrera. *Non linear filters for image processing*, chapter Binary logical operators. SPIE and IEEE Press, 1998.
- [12] N. S. T. Hirata, E. R. Dougherty, and J. Barrera. Efficient Switching Algorithm for Designing Increasing Binary Filters. In E. R. Dougherty and J. T. Astola, editors, *Nonlinear Image Processing X*, volume 3646 of *Proc. SPIE*, pages 185–196, San Jose, CA, January 1999.
- [13] N. S. T. Hirata, E. R. Dougherty, and J. Barrera. A Switching Algorithm for Design of Optimal Increasing Binary Filters Over Large Windows. *Pattern Recognition*, 33(6):1059–1081, June 2000. Special Issue on Mathematical Morphology & Nonlinear Image Processing.
- [14] J. Barrera., E. R. Dougherty, and M. Brun. Hybrid human-machine binary morphological operator design. an independent constraint approach. *Signal Processing*, 2000.
- [15] Edward R. Dougherty, J. Barrera, Gerard Mozelle, Seungchan Kim, and Marcel Brun. Multiresolution analysis for optimal binary filters. submitted, January 2000.
- [16] V. G. Kamat, E. R. Dougherty, and J. Barrera. Multiresolution Bayesian Design of Binary Filters. *submitted*, 2000.